

ISic4425

Inscribed boundary stone

Language

Latin

Type

terminus

Material

volcanic

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,system,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

none

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Paternò

Provenance

The only record is in the manuscript collection of Gaetano Marini, whence later editions. Marini records it as being found in the 'ager Catinensis', in the locale known as 'le Timpe', and in his time preserved in front of the church of the village of Sferri

Coordinates

37.501100, 14.796780

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, lost

Physical Description

Described as a quadrangular column of volcanic stone by Marini

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Inscriptions are recorded on two faces, divided over two and three lines in the account of Marini

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

No information is preserved

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text**Apparatus**

Text from Marini

The line above the letters omitted in all later editions

The line above the letters omitted in all later editions

Mai: KAT

Translation**Commentary**

In contrast to other examples (ISic1338 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/>]

inscription/ISic1338] , ISic1404 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1404>] , ISic4424 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4424>]) the text of this inscription appears to be written clearly in Latin letters. Nonetheless the presence of variations on the same formulation of $\overline{\text{EKL}}$ KAT which is found also in those texts, and the broadly similar geographical area of origin, strongly suggest that this stone (and also ISic4426 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4426>] and ISic4427 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4427>] reported with it by Marini) has a similar context, namely as a boundary stone relating to the lands of the early church in Sicily. Like Pace before him, Ferrua interpreted these in this way, and expands ECL as *ecclesiae* and KAT as *Katinensis*. This text, together with ISic4426 and ISic4427, is only reported by Gaetano Marini, and the texts in Angelo Mai, Pace, and Ferrua all derive directly from this one record. Pace understood Marini to refer to four sides of a single stone, but Ferrua more reasonably interprets the annotations of Marini to refer firstly to two sides of one stone ('hinc', 'inde'), as reported in this edition; and then to two further separate texts ('item altera inscripta' and 'item altera reperta in agro'). It is not impossible that the latter two texts reported by Marini (here ISic4426 and ISic4427) are in fact the same as the two recorded by Gulatherus (ISic1338 and ISic4424), but the differences are sufficient to suggest not.

The date of the stone is very difficult to ascertain. If the interpretation suggested by Ferrua is adopted, making this one of several boundary markers for church property from the wider area of the Catania hinterland, then a date of the fifth century AD or later seems likely. It would be possible to accept the reading of KAT as referring to Catania, without accepting the need to interpret ECL or EKL as a reference to the church.

Digital identifiers:

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4425>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4022743

Bibliography

Mai, Angelo 1831. *Scriptorum veterum nova collectio e vaticani codicibus edita*. Rome. At p.352 no.5

Pace, B. 1949. *Arte e civiltà della Sicilia antica*. Volume quarto. Barbari e Bizantini. Rome, Naples, Città di Castello. At 225 n.2

Ferrua, A 1989. *Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia*. Vatican. At 123-124 no.471

Manganaro, G. 1994. *Per una storia della 'chora Katanaia'*. In Olshausen, E., Sonnabend, H.(eds.), *Stuttgarter Kolloquium zur historischen Geographie des Altertums 4 (1990) / Geographica Historica 7. Herausgegeben von Ernst Kirsten..* Amsterdam: Verlag Adolf M. Hakkert. pp. 127-174. At 174 n.175

Licensed under a Creative Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-21): ISic4425. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4381968>